

Preliminary Standarization of *Murvadi Agada*

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ABSTRACT: In the *Agada Tantra*, *Gara visha* is associated with any substance, synthetic or artificial in origin, that harms the body directly or through its toxic metabolites. *Acharya Susrutha* mentions different types of poisoning in *Garadhishtana*. In modern times, people are consciously or unconsciously exposed to different types of poisons, natural or artificial in origin. In this case, *Mūrvādi Agada* of the *Ashtanga Hridaya Uttarasthana Vishapratisheda* chapter is recommended in the context of *Garavisha*. *Mūrvādi Agada* is a unique and useful formula specially formulated for Agni Vikaras.

INTRODUCTION

In the *Agada Tantra*, *Gara visha* is associated with any substance, synthetic or artificial in origin, that harms the body directly or through its toxic metabolites. *Acharya Susrutha* mentions different types of poisoning in *Garadhishtana*. In modern times, people are consciously or unconsciously exposed to different types of poisons, natural or artificial in origin. In this case, *Mūrvādi Agada* of the *Ashtanga Hridaya Uttarasthana Vishapratisheda* chapter is recommended in the context of *Garavisha*. *Mūrvādi Agada* is a unique and useful formula specially formulated for Agni Vikaras.

It is a composite herbal formulation described in the context of "*Garopahat Paavaka*". Symptoms resulting from disorder of *Agni* due to administration of *Gara Visha*. This recipe is the only contribution of *Asthanga Karas* and has not been described anywhere else. *Mūrvādi Agada* should be administered along with *Anupanas* like *Ushana Jala*, *Takra*, *Mastu* and *Amla Rasa Dravyas*. Symptoms of *Gara Visha* can occur even in modern times due to the addition of toxic substances like animal excrement, poisonous medicines, *Viruddha Aushadhi* etc. to food.

In today's situation, all junk foods, colourings, food additives, preservatives, processed foods and drinks can be consumed as *Garavisha*. This can lead to *Agni Vikaras* (indigestion) like *Sthoulya*, *Arsha*, *Atisara* and *Udara Rogas*. *Mūrvādi Agada* when administered with proper *Anupana* is effective against these diseases.

Mūrvādi Agada references:

Asthanga Hridaya/Uttarasthana/35. Chapter

Asthanga Sangraha/Uttarasthana/40. Chapter

Drug profile

Sl no	Drug	Binomial Nomenclature	Family	Part used
1	<i>Mūrvā</i>	<i>Chonemorpha macrophylla</i> Roxb	Asclepidaceae	Root
2	<i>Amṛtā</i>	<i>Tinosporacordifoila</i> Miers	Menispermaceae	Stem
3	<i>Nata</i>	<i>Valeriana wallichii</i> Dc	Valerianaceae	Rhizome

4	<i>Pippalī</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn	Piperaceae	Fruit
5	<i>Paṭola</i>	<i>Trichosanthus dioica</i> Roxb	cucurbitaceae	Root
6	<i>Cavya</i>	<i>Piper chaba</i> Trel.Yunk	Piperaceae	Root
7	<i>Citrāka</i>	<i>Plumbago rosea</i> Linn	Plumbaginaceae	Root
8	<i>Vachā</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn	Araceae	Rhizome
9	<i>Mustā</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn	Cyperaceae	Tuber
10	<i>Viḍaṅga</i>	<i>Embelia Ribes</i> Burm.F	Myrsinaceae	Fruit

Physico-chemical parameters *Murvādi Agada*

Physicochemical parameters were done as part of preliminary standardization of the drug. Methodologies were based on the methods described pharmacopeia of India. Parameters like total ash value, acid insoluble ash, water insoluble ash, sulphated ash, pH value, loss on dry, were determined. The results of physico-chemical parameters of *Murvādi Agada* are shown in table

Physicochemical parameters	Result (gm) (Mean ± SE)
Total Ash	5.3 ± 0.18 w/w
Acid insoluble ash	5.03 ± 0.27w/w
Water insoluble ash	1.06 ± 0.06w/w
Sulphated ash	6.23 ± 0.26 w/w
Loss on drying	6.16 ± 0.26 at 29 ± 2.5 C
pH	4.16 ± 0.08 w/w

Phytochemical screening

The *Murvādi Agada* aqueous extract (MAAE) was subjected to phytochemical screening for major secondary metabolites by standardized internationally accepted protocols as described by Harborne (1967) Trease and Evans' and other pharmacopeial standards. The results of phytochemical screening of *Murvādi Agada* aqueous extract is shown in table

Test done	Reaction
Alkaloids	
Marqui's test	Negative
Wagner's test	Positive
Mayer's test	Negative
Froehd's test	Negaive
Dragendroff's test	Positive
Carbohydrates	
Fehling test	Positive
Molish test	Negative
Protein	
Nimhydrin test	Negative
Glycosides	
Legal's test	Positive
Keller-killiani test	Positive
10%NaoH test	Positive

Flavanoids	
Alkaline reagent test	Positive
Lead acetate test	Positive
Shinoda's test	Positive
Ferric chloride test	Negative
Tannins	
Ferric chloride test	Positive
Phytosterols	
Salkowski's test	Negative
Lieberman –Burchardt's test	Negative
Phenols	
Iodine test	Positive
Ferric chloride	Negative
Lead acetate test	Negative
Cardiac glycosides	
Keller-killiani test	Positive

HPTLC PROFILING

The phytochemicals were standardized by performing high performance thin layer chromatography of methanolic extract of *Murvādi Agada* in CAMA instrumentation and visualized at 254 and 366 nm UV light. In 254 nm visualization got 10 peaks with highest percentage area of 44.52 for peak 10. The lowest percentage area was 0.98 for peak 7. Similarly, in 366 nm 10 peaks were obtained with highest per area was 42.07 for peak no 10 and the lowest percentage area 1.18 which was obtained for peak 7. The corresponding Rf values for the highest peak in 254 nm was 0.94 and in 356 nm was 0.94. The results are shown in table and figure Rf value and area% of *Murvādi Agada* at 254 nm

HPTLC profiling at 254 nm

Peak	Max.Rf	Area	Area%
1	0.04	965.8	2.57
2	0.15	1203.1	3.20
3	0.20	1070.0	2.85
4	0.25	614.3	1.63
5	0.32	473.3	1.26
6	0.41	588.1	1.57
7	0.52	369.9	0.98
8	0.59	12569.6	33.45
9	0.71	2993.6	7.97
10	0.88	16728.3	44.52

Total number of peaks: 10

Maximum area obtained on: Peak 10

Overview graph of *Murvādi Agada* at 254nm

Rf value and area% of *Murvādi Agada* at 366 nm

Peak	Max.Rf	Area	Area%
1	0.03	1019.0	2.82
2	0.15	1318.8	3.65
3	0.20	817.9	2.26
4	0.25	696.5	1.93
5	0.33	559.5	1.55
6	0.40	672.3	1.86
7	0.51	427.2	1.18
8	0.60	12518.6	34.65
9	0.72	2897.9	8.02
10	0.89	15196.5	42.07

Total number of peaks: 10 Maximum area obtained on: Peak no.10

Overview graph of *Murvādi Agada* at 366 nm

LCMS PROFILING

Characterization of phytochemicals was done by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry using methanol extract of *Murvādi Agada*. A total of 261 compounds were found. Out of which 69 compounds were identified by name. Among this most of the compounds showed retention score between 81 to 89. Data processing of

molecular ions obtained by ESI and APCI mass fragmentation led to the identification of several phytoconstituents belonging to various classes of compounds such as phenolics, flavonoids, and coumarins and glycosides

List of identified compounds are shown in table

Compounds	Compounds
AminoDHQ	Isoswertisin 2"-Orhamnoside
Benzyl methyl disulfide	-)-Deltoin
L-Galactonate	Swerchirin
2-C-Methyl-D-erythritol4-phosphate	Quercetin
3-Dehydro-L-threonate	Formononetin 7-(6"-methylmalonylglucoside
(R)-3,3-Dimethylmalate	Calendoflaside
Diethyl sulfate	syringaresinol
Wistin	3,4-Dicaffeoyl-1,5-quinolactone
2-(Ethoxymethyl)phenol	5-O-p-
Coumaroylnigrumin	
Pisumoside B	Premithramycin A1
Phymarolin I	Pecorin 5
4-O-beta-D-Glucosylsinapate	9S,11R,15S-trihydroxy-2,3-dinor-13Eprostaenoic acidcyclo[8S,12R]
Picrasin E	Curcumin diglucoside
Scillaren A	4,11,13,15-Tetrahydridentin B
Caffeic aldehyde	Lepidine F
Bracteatin 6-O-glucoside	Gomphrenin II
Kanokoside A	Pecorin 5
Kanokoside D	Melilotussaponin O1
Graveolone	Gomphrenin II
Guajavarin	Kuwanone H
(1R,3S,4S,6R)-6,9-Dihydroxyfenchone6-Ob-D-glucoside	Palmatoside G
Scopolin	Gomphrenin II
Lophophorine	Piperolactam D
Genistin	Alanyl-Isoleucine
4-Hydroxycoumarin	Icariin
Scopolin	Adhulupone
3-Hydroxychavicol 1-[rhamnosyl-(1->6)-glucoside]	5-Megastigmen-7-yne-3,9-diol 9-glucoside
Nonate	6-Gingerol
Coixinden A	DL-2-hydroxy valeric acid
Allyl phenoxyacetate	3-Ketoapotrichothecene
7,8-Dihydrovomifoliol 9-	Baicalein

[apiosyl-(1->6)-glucoside]	
9alpha-Fluoro-	Spironolactone
6alphamethylprednisolone	21-
acetate	
Lauroilsine	9,10-Epoxy-18-
	hydroxystearate
3-oxo-tetradecanoic acid	Glaucarubin
Fumigaclavine A	

CONCLUSION

Murvadi Agada is a unique and useful formulation, which is specifically prescribed for *Agni Vikara*'s. It is a compound herbal preparation that is explained under the context of "*Garopahata Paavaka*" i.e., a condition which is a result of impaired *Agni* caused due to administration of *Gara visha*. The formulation is a sole contribution of *Asthanga Kara*'s which is not explained elsewhere.

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